

THE IMPACT OF ROLE PLAYING AND DRAMATIZATION ON LINGUOCREATIVITY IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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ABSTRACT:

In the era of globalization, the need for innovative and interactive approaches to language teaching has increased significantly. Traditional grammatical and translation-based methods cannot fully meet the communicative needs of students. This article analyzes the need for interactive methods such as role-playing, dramatization, and collaborative learning. Based on theoretical sources and empirical research, it is considered how interactive approaches affect the development of linguocreativity, motivation, and real-life communication skills.

Keywords: Language teaching, globalization, interactive methods, role-playing, linguocreativity, motivation, communicative approach, student activity, dramatization.

ANNOTATSIYA:

Globalizatsiya davrida til o'qitishda innovatsion va interaktiv yondashuvlarga bo'lgan ehtiyoj sezilarli darajada oshdi. An'anaviy grammatik va tarjimaga asoslangan usullar o'quvchilarning kommunikativ ehtiyojlarini to'liq qondira olmaydi. Ushbu maqolada rol o'ynash, dramatizatsiya va hamkorlikda o'rganish kabi interaktiv metodlarning zarurati tahlil qilinadi. Nazariy manbalar va empirik tadqiqotlar asosida interaktiv yondashuvlarning lingvokreativlik, motivatsiya va real hayotdagi muloqot qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishga qanday ta'sir etishi ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Til o'qitish, globalizatsiya, interaktiv metodlar, rol o'ynash, lingvokreativlik, motivatsiya, kommunikativ yondashuv, o'quvchilarning faolligi, dramatizatsiya.

The globalization process requires the continuous integration of information, technology and education systems on a global scale. In particular, the transition from traditional methods to interactive approaches in the process of teaching a foreign language is becoming increasingly important. In the context of globalization, English

is becoming not only a means of international communication, but also a key tool for education, business and scientific research. Therefore, students should not be limited to just grammatically correct mastery of the language, but also be able to use it in real-life situations. This increases the need for interactive and communicative approaches.

While traditional language teaching methods are often based on grammatical rules and translation, interactive approaches ensure the active participation of students. For example: While traditional methods are considered to be memorizing theoretical rules, translating, and performing written exercises, interactive methods can be said to be learning through discussion, role-playing, dramatization, and practical projects.⁴⁷

As Chamorro Cifuentes's research has shown, interactive methods, especially role-playing and dramatization, are important in increasing students' motivation to learn a language when their level of English communication is low. The facts and results presented in the article confirm the importance of role-playing techniques in increasing linguocreativity and motivation.⁴⁸

If we examine the research work of Dhea Mizhir Krebt, we can determine that role-playing techniques are more effective than traditional teaching methods and significantly improve students' speaking skills. The results of the study show that through role-playing techniques, students have the opportunity to consolidate their knowledge and freely express their thoughts. In addition, it confirms that interactive methods in higher education also serve to increase students' motivation and develop their linguocreative thinking skills.⁴⁹

Innovative approaches to language learning are very effective, and not only grammatical knowledge is sufficient to develop students' speaking skills, but also communicative approaches are required. Role-playing and dramatization methods are recognized as important tools in language teaching for developing students' linguistic creativity. For example, when students are given a simulation of a restaurant environment, they take on the roles of a customer and a staff member; in the process, their ability to ask for orders, describe, and create new vocabulary in personal communication increases. In such situations, students are required to develop original

⁴⁷ Sternberg, R. J., & Lubart, T. I. (1999). The concept of creativity: Prospects and paradigms. In R. J. Sternberg (Ed.), *Handbook of Creativity* (pp. 3–15). Cambridge University Press

⁴⁸ Chamorro-Cifuentes, J. X. (2024). Juego de roles: técnica para mejorar la comunicación en lengua extranjera. *Revista Criterios*, 31(1), 89-104. <https://doi.org/10.31948/rc.v31i1.3856>

⁴⁹ Krebt, D. M. (2024). The effectiveness of role play techniques in teaching speaking for EFL college students, 2023, 44.

and creative speech forms that are appropriate for real-life contexts. Also, dramatization tasks, for example, by reenacting a scene from a literary work, students master different intonations, emotions, and speech structures, and combine language elements in innovative ways. These methods allow students to independently recreate the content and structure of the language, and also increase their metalinguistic awareness. As a result, teaching using interactive methods increases students' interest in the language and helps to further strengthen their linguo-creative thinking potential.

In conclusion, the results of this study show that interactive methods in teaching English, in particular role-playing and dramatization, are effective tools for significantly increasing students' linguistic creativity and motivation. Interactive approaches enliven the language learning process and serve to strengthen students' communicative skills and metalinguistic awareness. It has also been proven that the widespread use of interactive methods can increase the effectiveness of foreign language teaching in the context of globalization.

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